

Consciousness as Temporal Integration: *An Astrocyte-Centered Framework for Understanding Experience*

Abstract

This work presents a novel framework for understanding consciousness through an astrocyte-centered model of temporal integration, situated within the free energy principle and Global Workspace Theory (GWT). Traditionally viewed as support cells, astrocytes are proposed here as active modulators in cognitive processing, functioning as “precision modulators” that dynamically adjust the gain of prediction error signals in neural circuits. By responding to neuromodulatory cues and metabolic demands, astrocytes selectively amplify or dampen prediction errors, facilitating a context-dependent filtering mechanism that prioritizes behaviorally relevant information. This modulatory role is hypothesized to underpin a “metabolic now”—a dynamic temporal window wherein astrocytes allocate metabolic resources to sustain conscious content within the global workspace, thereby supporting the temporal coherence and stability of conscious experience. Additionally, the model explores the philosophical implications of a temporally structured consciousness, drawing on Bergson’s concept of *durée*, suggesting that subjective experience arises from the brain’s recursive organization of time. Through a synthesis of predictive coding, metabolic regulation, and philosophical insights, this astrocyte-centered theory redefines consciousness as a dynamically sustained, temporally structured flow of information, offering a fresh perspective on the integration of neural and metabolic processes in the emergence of subjective awareness.

Precision and Astrocytes

In the brain, neurons play the central role in encoding and transmitting information, making them the fundamental units of computation and communication. Neurons process sensory inputs and generate outputs through electrical signals, but this process isn’t merely a direct relay. Instead, neurons actively integrate incoming signals based on their relevance and reliability, enabling the brain to operate efficiently and avoid overloading on irrelevant noise. This is achieved through “precision weighting” in predictive coding, a computational framework where the brain constantly generates predictions about incoming sensory information and updates its internal models based on the discrepancy—prediction errors—between expectation and reality. Prediction errors indicate where the brain’s expectations are misaligned with sensory inputs, triggering an update to the predictive model. However, not all prediction errors are equally relevant; some reflect minor discrepancies that don’t require the brain’s full resources, while others signal critical mismatches that demand attention. Neurons dynamically adjust the “gain” on these errors, determining how strongly they impact subsequent processing and model updates.

Precision weighting is the mechanism by which neurons regulate the impact of prediction errors, selectively amplifying or dampening signals based on their inferred reliability and importance. This weighting process relies on neuromodulatory input from neurotransmitters like dopamine, norepinephrine, and acetylcholine, which convey essential contextual information about the organism’s physiological state, emotional status, and environmental demands. Neurons in higher-order cortical areas prioritize certain inputs over others, enabling the brain to allocate cognitive resources to the most behaviorally significant information. For instance, under threat

or high-stress conditions, norepinephrine levels rise, increasing the precision weighting of certain prediction errors, particularly those associated with threat detection and rapid response. Conversely, when an error is less relevant to immediate needs, the precision assigned to it is lower, effectively down-weighting its influence and preventing unnecessary cognitive recalibration.

Neurons handle the active encoding and modulation of prediction errors, while precision weighting ensures that the brain's limited resources are allocated where they're most needed. However, neurons do not act alone; astrocytes, long thought to be support cells, may play a critical role in this process by adjusting precision weights based on contextual cues. The proposed model suggests that astrocytes act as precision modulators that fine-tune the gain of prediction errors in response to a range of cues, including neuromodulators, metabolic states, and patterns of activity in neighboring neurons. By releasing neuroactive substances like gliotransmitters and metabolic factors, astrocytes can amplify or dampen prediction errors, complementing neuronal processing by influencing which errors are prioritized or suppressed. This synergy between neurons and astrocytes provides a more flexible and context-sensitive mechanism for precision weighting, enabling a dynamic partnership where astrocytes serve as gatekeepers that tailor prediction error weighting based on broader contextual relevance. Together, neurons and astrocytes collaboratively maintain a system of precision weighting that maximizes predictive efficiency and cognitive relevance, forming a robust platform for dynamic, context-dependent processing.

The Contextual Guidance theory, published first as a perspective article by Murphy-Royal, Ching, and Papouin (2022), suggests astrocytes serve as active participants in a feedforward mechanism that tailors neural circuit activity based on specific internal or external contextual cues (Murphy-Royal, Ching, & Papouin, 2022). My framework aims to extend the contextual guidance theory. In my framework and within the framework of the free energy principle, this feedforward mechanism can be conceptualized as astrocytes modulating the precision (gain) assigned to prediction error signals in neural circuits involved in predictive coding. Astrocytes detect "contextual triggers" such as neuromodulators (e.g., norepinephrine), metabolic cues, or peripheral afferents, which activate them in a circuit-specific manner. These contextual triggers can be interpreted as signals that indicate the presence of prediction errors or discrepancies between the brain's top-down predictions and bottom-up sensory inputs. Upon activation by these contextual triggers, astrocytes release "contextualizers," including gliotransmitters (e.g., glutamate, D-serine, ATP) and metabolic signals (e.g., lactate, adenosine). These contextualizers act as effector mechanisms that modify the activity of neural circuits involved in predictive coding, effectively adjusting the precision weighting assigned to the prediction error signals processed by those circuits. For example, if a particular contextual trigger (e.g., a specific pattern of neuromodulator release) indicates that a certain prediction error is highly relevant to the organism's current state or needs, astrocytes can release contextualizers that increase the precision (gain) assigned to that prediction error signal. This amplification would prioritize the propagation and updating of internal models based on that specific prediction error, facilitating more efficient free energy minimization.

Conversely, if a contextual trigger signifies that a prediction error is less relevant or informative, astrocytes can release contextualizers that decrease the precision assigned to that error signal, effectively suppressing its impact on belief updating and resource allocation.

By integrating contextual information from neuromodulators and other cues, astrocytes can dynamically modulate the precision weighting of prediction error signals across the brain's hierarchical architecture. This context-dependent precision modulation optimizes the free energy minimization process by ensuring that computational resources are strategically allocated to the most relevant or informative prediction errors, while uninformative errors are down weighted or ignored.

Astrocytes do not directly detect or encode prediction errors themselves. Instead, they are sensitive to various contextual cues that indirectly signal the presence and relevance of prediction errors in different neural circuits. These contextual cues can include neuromodulators, neurotransmitters, metabolic states, and patterns of neural activity, among others.

The key idea is that astrocytes exhibit regional and functional heterogeneity, which makes them differentially responsive to specific contextual cues in different brain areas. This heterogeneity is proposed to align with the distinct computational demands and predictive processing roles of the neural circuits they are associated with.

For example, astrocytes in primary sensory cortices might be tuned to contextual cues that signal the presence of prediction errors related to low-level sensory features. In contrast, astrocytes in higher-order association areas might be more sensitive to cues that indicate prediction errors related to more abstract, multimodal representations.

When astrocytes detect these context-specific cues, they respond by releasing neuroactive substances (gliotransmitters) and adjusting their metabolic support to the surrounding neural tissue. These astrocytic outputs, in turn, modulate the excitability and synaptic processing of the neurons computing prediction errors, effectively adjusting the gain or precision weighting of those error signals.

So, rather than directly detecting prediction errors, astrocytes rely on their specialized sensitivity to contextual cues that serve as proxies or correlates of prediction error signals in different brain regions. They then modulate the precision or gain of those error signals indirectly, by altering the responsiveness and processing dynamics of the neurons that encode and propagate them.

This allows astrocytes to align their modulatory influence with the specific predictive processing demands of different neural systems, based on the unique contextual cues available in each region. The regional heterogeneity of astrocytes thus enables them to implement context-dependent precision modulation across the brain's hierarchical predictive processing architecture.

Astrocytes as Precision Modulators in the Free Energy Principle

Astrocytes express a diverse repertoire of receptors for neurotransmitters, neuromodulators, and metabolites, as well as ion channels and transporters. This allows them to detect a wide range of contextual cues that signify specific discrepancies between the brain's top-down predictions and bottom-up sensory inputs (prediction errors). Different combinations of these cues can indicate the presence and nature of particular prediction errors. Astrocytes are highly sensitive to neuromodulatory signals, such as dopamine, norepinephrine, and acetylcholine, which convey information about the organism's physiological state, emotional state, and

environmental conditions. By integrating these neuromodulatory signals, astrocytes can assess the broader context in which prediction errors occur, allowing them to modulate the precision weighting accordingly.

Rather than directly encoding or recognizing prediction errors, astrocytes exhibit contextual sensitivity and act as dynamic precision modulators. They can amplify or dampen the responses of neural circuits to prediction errors based on the contextual relevance signaled by the integrated cues. This allows them to selectively emphasize or suppress the impact of certain prediction errors on neural processing and belief updating. Astrocytes are interconnected through gap junctions, enabling them to coordinate their responses across spatially distributed networks. This network-level influence allows astrocytes to globally modulate the precision weighting of prediction error signals, ensuring that precision modulation is coherent and contextually appropriate across interconnected brain regions. Astrocytes' ability to modulate prediction error precision is highly adaptive. They can adjust the precision weighting based on the organism's changing needs, priorities, and objectives. For instance, astrocytes might amplify the precision of prediction errors related to potential threats in one context and dampen the precision of errors related to reward prediction in another, depending on the current behavioral context signaled by neuromodulators.

By leveraging these mechanisms, astrocytes can act as context-dependent precision modulators within the free energy principle framework. They can dynamically adjust the precision (gain) assigned to prediction error signals based on the integrated contextual information, without directly participating in the computation of prediction errors themselves. This precision modulation optimizes the brain's free energy minimization efforts by emphasizing or suppressing the propagation and updating of internal models based on the contextual relevance of the prediction errors.

Astrocytes serve as context-dependent precision modulators in the brain's free energy minimization process. By integrating various contextual cues, including neuromodulators, metabolic signals, and patterns of neural activity, astrocytes dynamically adjust the precision weighting assigned to prediction errors across the brain's hierarchical architecture. This astrocyte-mediated precision modulation optimizes the brain's free energy minimization efforts by amplifying or suppressing prediction error signals based on their relevance to the organism's current state and needs.

Astrocytes as Precision Modulators in GWT

The Global Workspace Theory (GWT) posits that conscious experience arises from the integration and broadcasting of selected information across a global network of neural regions. At its core, GWT suggests that only the most salient and behaviorally relevant information gains access to this "global workspace" — a distributed system of cortical and subcortical circuits that share information with many parts of the brain simultaneously. This broadcasting mechanism is thought to enable integrated processing, allowing different cognitive functions, such as perception, memory, and executive control, to access and work with a unified pool of information. In this view, consciousness is the result of widespread access to high-salience signals within the global workspace, allowing the brain to coordinate complex actions, make

decisions, and form coherent subjective experiences. Neurons play a central role in this model by selectively encoding and amplifying signals that meet a certain threshold of significance, effectively setting the stage for information to enter the conscious mind.

The selection of information for conscious broadcast relies heavily on the mechanism of precision weighting. Precision weighting functions as a kind of attentional filter, where certain signals—typically prediction errors that reflect mismatches between expectation and sensory input—are selectively amplified based on their contextual relevance. Neurons assign higher precision to prediction errors that carry critical or surprising information, effectively determining which signals are given priority in the competitive process for entry into the global workspace. This weighting process is mediated by neuromodulators such as dopamine and norepinephrine, which adjust the gain of neuronal responses based on context. In situations of heightened attention or urgency, neuromodulators raise the precision of signals relevant to the current goals or challenges, amplifying their impact on the neural hierarchy and increasing the likelihood of their entry into the workspace. Through this mechanism, precision weighting enables neurons to prioritize only the most reliable and contextually relevant information for widespread broadcasting, filtering out noise and conserving cognitive resources.

Once a signal has been assigned high precision and gains access to the global workspace, it is rapidly propagated across brain regions through long-range cortico-cortical connections, creating a widespread neural activation pattern often referred to as “neuronal ignition.” This ignition process is characterized by a sharp rise in synchronized neural activity, particularly in high-level areas such as the prefrontal cortex, which plays a key role in coordinating and sustaining conscious content. Ignition enables the integration of diverse types of information—from sensory data to emotional cues and motor plans—into a coherent and accessible mental representation. However, conscious broadcasting is metabolically expensive: neurons require substantial energy to sustain the high firing rates necessary for global access and maintain synchronization across distributed networks. This energy demand underscores the brain's need to allocate metabolic resources selectively, sustaining only those neural circuits deemed most significant by the precision-weighting process.

Metabolic support, primarily supplied by astrocytes, is crucial for sustaining the neural activity involved in global broadcasting. Astrocytes regulate local blood flow, shuttle glucose, and deliver lactate to neurons through the astrocyte-neuron lactate shuttle (ANLS), a process that facilitates rapid ATP production. This metabolic support, which constitutes the “metabolic now,” ensures that neurons broadcasting high-precision signals receive the necessary energy to maintain persistent, synchronized firing. Neurovascular coupling, where astrocytes signal blood vessels to dilate in response to local neuronal activity, further guarantees that active regions receive an increased supply of oxygen and glucose. By allocating metabolic resources preferentially to the circuits broadcasting high-precision signals, astrocytes help sustain the neuronal ignition needed for conscious access, effectively stabilizing the content within the global workspace long enough to enable extended processing and integration.

Thus, precision weighting and metabolic support work together to govern which information gains access to consciousness. Precision weighting, orchestrated by neurons and neuromodulators, initially selects signals based on their relevance, setting the groundwork for global broadcast. Once selected, these high-precision signals demand substantial metabolic support to maintain the prolonged and synchronized neural activity characteristic of conscious broadcasting. Astrocytes, sensitive to the metabolic needs of active neurons, ensure that these high-priority signals receive the resources necessary for sustained integration within the global workspace. Together, precision weighting and metabolic support create a dynamic system where only the most contextually significant signals achieve the level of activation required for conscious access. In this way, GWT relies not just on neural mechanisms of signal selection, but on an energetically constrained process where metabolic resources shape and sustain the contents of consciousness, underscoring the brain's need for efficient and adaptive resource allocation.

The Global Workspace Theory posits that conscious experience arises from the entry of information into a global workspace - a distributed neural process that enables integrated and broadcasted processing across many brain regions. Only the most salient information gains access to this global workspace. Astrocytes could serve as key modulators or "gatekeepers" governing which information enters the global workspace by virtue of their ability to contextually amplify or suppress prediction error signaling. Astrocytes continuously integrate contextual cues (neuromodulators, metabolic states, neural activity etc.) to assess the salience and relevance of different streams of incoming prediction errors for the organism. Based on this integrated context, astrocytes dynamically adjust the precision weighting assigned to the prediction error signals propagating across cortical hierarchies. Prediction errors that are amplified and assigned high precision weights by astrocytes become more likely to drive widespread neural responses, belief updating, and entry into the hypothesized global workspace. Conversely, prediction errors that are suppressed and assigned low precision by astrocytes remain more localized and are less likely to instigate the kind of large-scale broadcasting and cognitive integration associated with conscious access.

This astrocyte-mediated precision modulation could act as an essential filter or "gateway" that selects which information rises to the level of conscious cognition based on its contextual importance for the organism's homeostatic regulation. The specific signatures of astrocytic activity patterns, coupled with resulting neural synchronization and metabolic dynamics, may contribute to the distinctive phenomenological qualities of different conscious experiences. In this view, the global workspace emerges from the brain's broader imperative to efficiently minimize free energy/surprise in a metabolically affordable manner. Astrocytes could enable this by precision-weighting prediction errors to selectively drive widespread belief propagation focused on the most relevant predictive variables given the current state.

The contents of the global workspace then are determined by the selective amplification and broadcasting of high-precision, informationally rich signals. The precision weighting of incoming sensory signals and their associated prediction errors is what determines which information gets access to the global workspace and becomes consciously available.

Here's how this process might work:

Sensory signals and prediction errors are generated at various levels of the cortical hierarchy, based on the brain's current predictive models and the incoming sensory input.

Astrocytes, in coordination with other neural mechanisms, assign precision weights to these signals based on their estimated reliability, contextual relevance, and informativeness.

High-precision signals are selectively amplified, while low-precision signals are attenuated or filtered out.

The precision-weighted signals are then propagated up the cortical hierarchy, competing for access to the global workspace. Signals with higher precision weights are more likely to be selected for global broadcasting, as they are deemed more informative and relevant to the brain's current predictive models and behavioral goals.

Once a signal reaches a certain threshold of activation and is selected for global broadcasting, it is rapidly propagated across multiple brain regions via long-range cortico-cortical connections, becoming available for conscious processing and report.

The globally broadcasted signal is then integrated with other conscious contents, forming a coherent, unified representation of the current state of the world and the organism. This integrated representation is what constitutes the content of conscious experience at any given moment.

In this view, precision weighting acts as a gating mechanism for the global workspace, determining which signals are prioritized for conscious processing based on their estimated precision and relevance. The selective amplification of high-precision signals by astrocytes and other neural mechanisms is what allows for the dynamic updating of the global workspace,

The interface between astrocyte-mediated precision modulation and global information broadcasting can be conceptualized as a dynamic, multi-scale process. At the local level, astrocytes adjust the gain of neural populations encoding prediction errors, effectively setting their 'volume' in the competition for global access. As these high-precision signals propagate, they trigger cascading activation across distributed neural networks. This propagation is facilitated by long-range astrocytic networks, which coordinate precision weighting across brain regions through calcium waves and gliotransmitter release. When a critical threshold of activation is reached, involving both the strength of the signal and the extent of its distribution, it triggers a phase transition in global brain dynamics. This transition, marked by sudden changes in large-scale neural synchronization and metabolic activity patterns, corresponds to the 'ignition' of the global workspace. In this state, the high-precision information becomes widely accessible, maintained in an active state through recurrent excitation and sustained metabolic support from astrocytes. This astrocyte-mediated mechanism thus serves not only to select content for consciousness but also to stabilize and maintain it within the global workspace, allowing for prolonged conscious access and manipulation of the information.

Neuronal Ignition and Precision Weighting

Neurons play the central role in the ignition of the global workspace. Once neurons encoding prediction errors reach a certain threshold of activation—due to high precision weighting—they propagate their signals to higher-level cortical areas. This propagation leads to widespread neural synchrony, allowing the brain to globally integrate information and broadcast it across

various regions. This is the moment when conscious awareness emerges: the most precise and relevant information wins out, gets integrated, and is made globally accessible.

The process of ignition is rapid, often occurring on the millisecond scale, and is heavily dependent on neural circuits in areas such as the prefrontal cortex and thalamus, which serve as key hubs for broadcasting information to distributed networks. Neurons, through this ignition process, determine which content becomes conscious and which stays below the threshold of awareness.

Astrocytes support this ignition by creating the "metabolic now," a momentary window where metabolic resources are directed toward high-precision, contextually relevant neural circuits. This allows neurons to sustain the high firing rates necessary for global broadcast. Astrocytes regulate the energy flow, ensuring that neurons involved in processing high-precision signals receive sufficient glucose and oxygen to maintain their activity. This metabolic support is crucial because conscious access is metabolically expensive—neurons require substantial energy to sustain the firing needed for global integration.

The preferential allocation of metabolic resources to high-precision prediction errors could give them a competitive advantage over lower-precision errors in the competition for access to the global workspace. With more metabolic support, high-precision errors may be able to sustain stronger and more coherent activation patterns, making them more likely to be selected for global broadcast.

The metabolic prioritization of high-precision errors could facilitate their synchronization and binding across distributed brain regions. By providing a common metabolic "boost" to neural populations encoding related prediction errors, astrocytes may help to generate coherent, synchronous activation patterns that are more easily integrated into the global workspace. The enhanced metabolic support for high-precision errors could make them more salient and attention-grabbing, increasing their likelihood of being consciously perceived. This could be mediated by the impact of metabolic signaling on neuromodulatory systems involved in attention and arousal.

The broadcast and integration of conscious contents in the global workspace may be associated with a global synchronization of metabolic activity across widespread brain regions. This could manifest as coordinated fluctuations in blood flow, glucose uptake, or oxygen consumption that reflect the binding and integration of information. The "ignition" of the global workspace, whereby a threshold of activation is crossed and information is rapidly propagated across the brain, may have a distinct metabolic profile. This could involve a sudden, coordinated uptick in metabolic resource allocation across distributed regions, reflecting the widespread activation and integration of conscious content.

Metabolic Now

The "metabolic now" emerges from the astrocyte-mediated precision weighting and temporal integration of prediction errors. Astrocytes, by selectively allocating metabolic resources to high-precision neural activity and facilitating sustained, synchronized firing across distributed networks, create a kind of "rolling window" of heightened processing that corresponds to the subjective present.

This metabolically enhanced period of high-precision activity is the threshold or gate for entry into the global workspace. Predictions that are assigned high precision and benefit from this

sustained metabolic support would be more likely to achieve the widespread broadcast and integration associated with conscious access.

In this view, the global workspace would be a kind of "metabolic spotlight" that shines on the most relevant, precise, and stable representations at each moment, making them available for flexible cognitive processing and behavior. The contents of consciousness would be determined by which prediction errors are prioritized and maintained by astrocytic modulation within this metabolic envelope.

The temporal boundaries of conscious experience, then, would be closely tied to the dynamics of metabolic resource allocation orchestrated by astrocytes. The "flow" of subjective time would reflect the ongoing progression of these high-precision, metabolically boosted states, with each "now" corresponding to a period of peak astrocytic modulation and neural synchronization. The metabolic now can be conceptualized as the "stage" or "threshold" of the global workspace. It represents the window of time during which information is made globally accessible and integrated across multiple brain regions through the coordinated action of astrocyte networks. During the metabolic now, the neural populations encoding the most precise, contextually relevant information receive preferential metabolic support, enabling them to generate stable, coherent activation patterns that are more likely to be broadcast widely and maintained within the global workspace.

The metabolic now provides the energetic and temporal foundation for the emergence of conscious content within the global workspace. It sets the stage for the integration and broadcasting of information, and its temporal boundaries define the "present moment" of conscious experience. The metabolic now could be seen as a mechanism for generating the kind of highly integrated, differentiated neural activity posited by IIT to underlie conscious states.

The metabolic now refers to a dynamic period of heightened metabolic activity driven by astrocytes, ensuring neurons have the necessary energy to sustain conscious thought and high-frequency firing. Central to this process is the astrocyte-neuron lactate shuttle (ANLS), where astrocytes take up glucose from the bloodstream, convert it into lactate via glycolysis, and shuttle it to neurons for rapid ATP production. This lactate supply enables neurons to maintain the energy-intensive firing required for tasks that demand focused attention and cognitive processing.

Another critical aspect of the metabolic now is neurovascular coupling, where astrocytes regulate blood flow by signaling blood vessels to dilate in response to neuronal activity. Astrocytes, through calcium signaling, release vasodilatory molecules like prostaglandins and nitric oxide, ensuring that active brain regions receive a continuous supply of oxygen and glucose. This modulation of blood flow supports the energy demands of neurons during peak activity, facilitating the metabolic resources needed for conscious experience.

Astrocytes also maintain ion homeostasis and neurotransmitter recycling, processes essential for preventing neuronal overexcitement and ensuring efficient synaptic activity. By taking up excess glutamate and regulating extracellular potassium levels, astrocytes prevent excitotoxicity and maintain the optimal conditions for sustained neuronal activity during the metabolic now.

These processes are energetically demanding and crucial for neurons to maintain functional stability over extended periods of high activity.

Finally, calcium signaling within astrocytic networks allows for the coordination of metabolic support across distributed brain regions. This enables astrocytes to synchronize energy allocation in response to changing cognitive demands, ensuring that the entire network involved in a task receives adequate metabolic support. By dynamically managing energy supply through these processes, astrocytes orchestrate the metabolic now, creating a physiological foundation for conscious experience and the flow of subjective time.

The precision weighting determined by astrocytes selects which prediction error signals are most relevant and contextually important, but it's the metabolic support provided by these same astrocytes that enables those signals to achieve the necessary level of activation for entry into the global workspace. Metabolic processes are essential for sustaining prolonged neural activity, not necessarily the initial trigger. The neuronal firing might spark the ignition of the global workspace, but the metabolic now provides the fuel for this conscious experience to persist and stay coherent. Energy allocation by astrocytes is what sustains and stabilizes the conscious present, making it possible for signals to stay in the global workspace long enough to influence cognition and behavior. In this view, the metabolic now is not just a passive background process but is actively shaping which information gets the metabolic support needed for global broadcasting. The metabolic spotlight that astrocytes create could help "ignite" the global workspace, by ensuring that the most relevant information has the energetic backing to rise to conscious awareness.

Elements of the "Metabolic Now" Signature:

Increased Glucose Uptake: This would be the hallmark of neurons receiving extra energy to sustain high-frequency firing. We'd expect to see increased glucose metabolism in regions where astrocytes have prioritized energy support, likely through the astrocyte-neuron lactate shuttle (ANLS).

Lactate Shuttling: Astrocytes convert glucose into lactate and then shuttle it to neurons for rapid ATP production. The signature might include increased lactate levels and high activity in metabolic pathways related to glycolysis within astrocytes.

Neurovascular Coupling and Blood Flow: In response to high neural activity, astrocytes regulate blood flow by signaling to blood vessels through mechanisms like calcium waves. We'd expect to see localized vasodilation and enhanced oxygen consumption in areas where the "metabolic now" is active, likely detectable via measures like fMRI BOLD signals.

Synchronized Metabolic Fluctuations: The temporal coordination of metabolic activity across distributed brain regions would be another signature. Astrocytes may synchronize their support of different neural circuits through calcium waves and long-range signaling, leading to synchronized increases in metabolic demand (e.g., glucose or oxygen).

Energy-Intensive Synaptic Maintenance: Ion homeostasis and neurotransmitter recycling are both energetically costly processes handled by astrocytes. In areas where astrocytes are actively regulating the "metabolic now," we would expect elevated activity related to maintaining the balance of extracellular ions and recycling glutamate to prevent excitotoxicity, all requiring high levels of ATP production.

Examples of Metabolic Activity in the "Metabolic Now":

Example 1: Focused Attention

During periods of focused attention (e.g., solving a math problem or reading intently), specific neural circuits are activated to maintain sustained cognitive focus.

Metabolic Signature:

High glucose uptake in areas related to attention, such as the prefrontal cortex and parietal regions.

Increased lactate production in astrocytes, shuttled to neurons to maintain high-frequency firing rates.

Localized increases in blood flow (neurovascular coupling) to regions that need extra metabolic support.

Astrocytic calcium waves synchronize metabolic support across different brain regions involved in attention, helping to maintain coherence and focus over time.

Metabolic Profile: In fMRI, you might see strong BOLD signals in attention-related areas, reflecting enhanced blood flow and oxygen consumption.

Example 2: Emotional Arousal (Fear Response)

In a situation where an individual experiences fear or arousal (e.g., during a threatening situation), the brain prioritizes prediction errors related to survival.

Metabolic Signature:

Elevated glucose uptake and lactate shuttling in regions like the amygdala and hypothalamus, which are involved in processing fear.

Heightened neurovascular coupling in these areas, with astrocytes signaling increased blood flow to provide extra resources to circuits responsible for threat detection and response.

Coordination of metabolic activity between regions like the prefrontal cortex (for decision-making) and the amygdala, allowing the emotional and cognitive components of fear to be integrated and acted upon.

Metabolic Profile: Increased glucose metabolism and oxygen consumption in the amygdala, seen via fMRI and PET scans, along with a surge in calcium signaling within astrocytes in the fear network.

Example 3: Resting State (Daydreaming)

During periods of rest or daydreaming, when the brain is not actively engaged in a specific task but is still processing internally generated thoughts (often linked to the default mode network).

Metabolic Signature:

Low-level glucose uptake across widespread brain areas, with moderate lactate production by astrocytes to maintain baseline metabolic support.

Moderate neurovascular coupling to sustain the default mode network, where astrocytes may help support ongoing low-level background activity without significant energy demand.

Low levels of synchronized metabolic activity, as there is less focus on highly precise prediction errors, and the brain is in a baseline state of energy consumption.

Metabolic Profile: fMRI might show lower BOLD signal intensity compared to states of high engagement, with lower fluctuations in glucose and oxygen uptake.

Qualia

The emergence of specific qualia—our subjective experiences like the redness of red or the sharpness of pain—results from precise temporal coordination and integration of neural activity within the brain's global workspace. Each quale is characterized by a unique temporal signature, meaning different experiences correspond to specific oscillatory patterns in terms of frequency and timing. The vividness and intensity of these qualia are determined by precision weighting, where highly precise and information-rich neural activity patterns are given prominence, resulting in more salient conscious experiences. This precision-weighted modulation, facilitated by astrocytes, not only influences which sensory inputs reach conscious awareness but also determines how strongly each experience impacts the stream of consciousness.

The "metabolic now" concept is crucial for bridging the spatial and temporal dimensions of qualia. This "now" represents a dynamic window of integrated information processing during which spatial relationships within our sensory experiences are continuously constructed and updated based on energy flow across the brain. Within this temporal window, neural populations encoding high-precision, contextually relevant information receive preferential metabolic support from astrocytes, which supply resources needed to stabilize and sustain coherent activation patterns. This astrocytic modulation gives rise to the spatial structure of specific qualia, such as the vibrancy of a color or the distinctness of a sound, effectively binding them within a stable frame of consciousness. The metabolic now ensures that circuits responsible for processing these high-precision qualia are sufficiently energized to maintain their presence in consciousness, allowing for a fully realized and temporally extended experience.

The global workspace acts as an integrative hub where these spatially and temporally structured qualia converge into a unified conscious field. As the metabolic now transitions from one moment to the next, it drives the continuous updating and binding of these spatially organized qualia, creating the fluidity of subjective experience. The self-model, acting as a stable attractor within this workspace, provides a consistent reference point amid the flux of qualia. Even as individual qualia emerge and fade, the self-model ensures a continuous sense of self, lending unity and cohesion to the changing contents of consciousness. This process enables a coherent and stable flow of subjective time, with each qualia serving as a temporal "snapshot" within this dynamic present.

Each phenomenal content that enters the global workspace marks a new moment in time, while the gradual fading and replacement of prior contents creates a palpable sense of temporal

progression. Precision-weighted qualia have a greater influence on this temporal structure, with high-precision qualia shaping the stream of consciousness more directly. This modulation by astrocytic networks allows certain qualia to act as key drivers of subjective time, determining the pace, rhythm, and texture of conscious experience. The richness and diversity of qualia, then, are not incidental but serve a functional role, equipping consciousness to navigate its informational landscape by differentiating between moments, prioritizing important events, and linking past experiences to present contexts.

Qualia are not arbitrary or epiphenomenal; they serve a critical functional role in guiding consciousness through the complex landscape of perception and memory. Each type of quale is distinguished by a unique temporal signature—a specific pattern of neural activity unfolding over time—which not only reflects but constitutes its subjective character. For instance, the experience of "redness" corresponds to a unique temporal pattern in color-sensitive visual areas, perhaps involving a rapid onset of high-frequency oscillations followed by sustained firing. This oscillatory signature is not simply correlated with the quale but directly produces its intensity and hue. In this way, qualia are adapted to serve as perceptual markers, guiding attention and action based on their predictive relevance within the brain's model of the environment.

Qualia further act as temporal markers that punctuate and structure the flow of experience, like signposts in a mental landscape. Over time, these temporal signatures serve to organize the coherence of subjective experience by acting as "stamps" on moments that differentiate them and contribute to a sense of narrative continuity. The temporal profile of each quale—its onset, duration, and transition—shapes not only its phenomenal quality but also its influence on behavior. A sudden onset, for example, signals an urgent attentional demand, while a prolonged experience allows for deeper integration and sustained focus. This dynamic interplay of temporal qualities among qualia structures the subjective experience of time, with faster-changing, novel stimuli leading to a sense of time passing quickly, while stable, predictable stimuli result in a more prolonged and cohesive experience.

By synchronizing multiple qualia within a single temporal moment, the brain can bind disparate sensory inputs—such as color, shape, and texture—into a coherent, multimodal perception. This temporal binding process allows the brain to unify various sensory modalities, providing the basis for the seamless experience of complex objects and events. Each quale's unique temporal signature creates a specific "marker" within consciousness that organizes and punctuates the stream of experience, establishing both the immediacy of the present moment and the flow from one experience to the next. Together, these temporally structured qualia weave the narrative of consciousness, maintaining the flow of subjective time and enabling the brain to continually adapt to its environment.

Self sustaining Loops

I propose there is a recursive dialogue between bodily states, astrocyte-mediated precision modulation, and localized metabolic regulation, forming a self-reinforcing loop:

1. Precision weights assigned to prediction errors influence belief updating and model refinement.
2. Neural activity associated with high-precision errors places a demand on energy resources.
3. Astrocytes, sensitive to metabolic need, increase blood flow, release lactate, etc., to support those neurons.

The self-sustaining nature of these loops is what allows certain experiences, or qualia, to have an enduring, autonomous presence in consciousness. This idea beautifully parallels how qualia themselves might operate: initially triggered by an external signal or internal prediction error, but sustained through recursive feedback loops between astrocytic modulation, metabolic support, and neural prioritization.

In this way, qualia become self-sustaining phenomena rather than transient, passive events. They persist in consciousness because they are actively supported and maintained by these self-reinforcing cycles of precision weighting, resource allocation, and astrocytic regulation. The outside signal or stimulus initiates the experience, but once it reaches a certain threshold of precision and metabolic support, it creates a kind of self-sustaining loop that reinforces its own presence in consciousness.

Here's how that might look in practice:

Initial Trigger and Precision Assignment: An external signal (such as a sudden sound or a strong visual cue) creates a high-precision prediction error that the brain deems significant. Astrocytes, tuned to the context, assign this signal high precision, amplifying its influence on the neural circuitry. This amplification primes the signal to be processed with heightened sensitivity.

Metabolic Support and Loop Stabilization: As the signal places demands on neural resources, astrocytes respond by increasing local metabolic support—blood flow, lactate, or other metabolites—to stabilize and sustain the activity. This support essentially “locks in” the signal, allowing it to persist. Because of this targeted resource allocation, the neural circuits encoding this signal maintain their activity longer, transforming it into a temporally extended experience.

Self-Sustaining Feedback Loop and Emergence of Qualia: Once this loop stabilizes, the experience becomes self-reinforcing. The astrocytic response keeps metabolic support flowing, which in turn sustains the neural activity and reinforces the prediction error's impact on the brain's predictive model. At this stage, the signal is no longer simply responding to the initial external trigger—it has achieved a self-sustaining status, where the metabolic and neural dynamics reinforce each other. This process could be what gives qualia their autonomous, vivid presence in consciousness, as they take on a life of their own within the brain's network.

Qualia as Autonomous Temporal Markers: In becoming self-sustaining, these qualia acquire an autonomous, almost object-like quality in consciousness. Like temporal landmarks, they

punctuate the flow of experience, acting as points of reference that the brain can use to structure other experiences. This self-sustaining nature explains why certain qualia are not just fleeting impressions but persistent, immersive experiences that command attention and shape our perception.

The Role of the Metabolic Now

The "metabolic now" plays a crucial role in ensuring that only the most relevant information is brought into conscious awareness. Since the brain has limited energy resources, it must prioritize which sensory inputs or cognitive processes are relevant in the moment. The metabolic now is the physiological mechanism by which the brain focuses its metabolic energy and attention on the most important information. This ensures that the brain allocates its resources to support cognition, behavior, and survival in the present moment.

The metabolic now can be thought of as the engine behind the conscious experience of the present. It sustains the perception of the present by providing the necessary energy and coherence for global integration. Not all information available at any given moment is equally relevant, and the metabolic now ensures that only the most contextually important information is prioritized and experienced.

Precision Weighting and Prioritization

Precision weighting, modulated by astrocytes, is the process by which the brain decides which sensory inputs and prediction errors are most important to focus on. It governs which prediction errors are amplified and integrated into consciousness, filtering out irrelevant or less critical information. By selectively amplifying certain sensory inputs and prediction errors, the brain ensures that only the most behaviorally relevant experiences are brought into conscious awareness.

This filtering process makes the brain's experience of time adaptive and efficient. Precision weighting ensures that the organism focuses on the most important and relevant aspects of the environment, helping to minimize unnecessary cognitive load or surprise.

Precision weighting and the Self

The self-model emerges from persistent embodied signals related to selfhood, such as visceral sensations and sense of body ownership. These signals represent ongoing prediction errors between the brain's model of the self and the actual internal/external state being perceived. Astrocytes play a role in this process by detecting these constant self-related signals and modulating their precision or gain. This precision-weighting ensures that neural populations encoding self-related signals receive prioritized computational resources and metabolic support. The stability and high precision of these self-related signals allow the self-model to be persistently activated and maintained in the global workspace, less susceptible to fluctuations from transient external inputs. This leads to a self-reinforcing loop: high precision weights cause self-models to increasingly drive global activity and resource allocation, prompting astrocytes to

further ramp up metabolic delivery. This creates self-sustaining cycles where metabolic expenditure and precision-weightings reciprocally increase, entrenching self-representations. As this process unfolds, the self-model becomes a high-dimensional attractor capturing conscious processing power. At a certain threshold of integration, metabolic expenditure, and precision-locking around the self-model, an irreducible, autonomous domain of conscious experience emergently arises. This self-model, now highly stable and persistent, begins to exert top-down control over other cognitive processes and behaviors.

The self-model influences consciousness in several ways. It modulates the precision-weighting of other prediction errors, effectively shaping the contents of conscious experience by determining which sensory inputs, thoughts, and emotions become salient. Experiences prioritized by the self-model receive greater metabolic support and are subjectively experienced as more vivid and intense, while suppressed experiences become faint or fleeting. This creates a "metabolic continuum" underlying the subjective vividness and stability of conscious contents. Furthermore, the self-model provides a stable framework that organizes the flow of thoughts, perceptions, and actions over time, contributing to the subjective sense of continuity and unity in conscious experience. Its autonomy and self-sustaining dynamics may underlie the subjective sense of being a distinct, unified entity – the "witness" of conscious experience. The self-model's ability to modulate its own activity also enables reflexive self-awareness, or the ability to take one's own conscious experiences as an object of awareness.

Through these mechanisms, the self-model becomes a central organizing principle of consciousness, shaping both the contents and quality of subjective experience. It acts as a stable, persistent "lens" through which the world is perceived and engaged with, prioritizing information and actions relevant to the organism's self-determined goals and needs. This process can be seen as a form of self-organization, where the interaction between bottom-up embodied signals and top-down predictive models, facilitated by astrocyte-mediated precision-weighting and metabolic regulation, gives rise to an emergent, autonomous self-model that constrains and guides the system's dynamics.

The Self-Model and Continuity of Consciousness

The self-model plays an essential role in creating a continuous sense of time across different moments. It serves as an anchor that ties together the brain's experience of time, maintaining a continuous perspective from which the flow of time is experienced. The self-model provides the organism with a consistent reference point, ensuring that time is experienced as a coherent, ongoing process, rather than a collection of disjointed moments.

Together, the global workspace and the self-model allow the brain to experience time as a seamless flow. They create the subjective "arrow of time," which moves forward through the continuous integration of relevant information and the maintenance of a stable self-reference.

Global integration is essential for the experience of time as a coherent, unified process. It binds local neural processes into a unified slice of the present, crucial for subjective time perception. The metabolic now provides the energy needed for this integration, ensuring that only the most contextually relevant information is brought into conscious experience.

Precision weighting acts as a filtering mechanism, determining which moments, inputs, or prediction errors should be prioritized for conscious awareness.

The self-model provides a continuous perspective that helps the brain experience time as an ongoing, seamless flow, creating the subjective impression of time moving forward.

Present now, metabolic now

To create a "now" that implies past and future necessarily involves the generation of subjective, qualitative experience. This is because the act of structuring time into a coherent present moment that contains implications of both past and future requires a perspective from which this structuring occurs. This perspective is inherently subjective, as it represents a unique vantage point from which time is organized and experienced.

The process of creating a "now" involves integrating current sensory inputs with memories of past events and predictions of future outcomes. This integration is not a passive recording of information, but an active process of selection, interpretation, and synthesis. The brain must decide which aspects of the past are relevant to the current moment, which potential futures are most likely or important, and how these elements relate to ongoing sensory experiences. This decision-making process, by its very nature, introduces a subjective element to the experience. Moreover, the act of bringing together past, present, and future into a single, coherent "now" necessitates a unifying framework - a "something it is like" to experience this integrated moment. This framework is what we experience as consciousness, with its attendant qualia. The qualitative aspects of experience - the redness of red, the painfulness of pain - can be understood as the specific ways in which different elements of past, present, and future are brought together in the creation of each moment of "now."

The "metabolic now" concept further supports this argument. The allocation of metabolic resources to support the neural activity involved in creating the "now" is not uniform or random, but prioritized based on relevance and importance to the organism. This prioritization process is inherently value-laden and perspective-dependent, further emphasizing the subjective nature of the "now."

The very act of creating a "now" that bridges past and future requires a locus of experience - a subjective "here" from which the temporal landscape is surveyed and structured. This locus of experience is precisely what we refer to as consciousness, complete with its qualitative, subjective aspects. Thus, the creation of a temporally structured "now" and the emergence of subjective experience are two sides of the same coin, inextricably linked in the ongoing process of consciousness.

Time itself is not inherently experiential. Rather, the experiential quality emerges when a complex system with a self-model structures time into a coherent "now." The self-model is key to this process. It provides the perspective or vantage point from which the "present now" is constructed and experienced. Consciousness arises from this act of "present-making" by a self-model. It's not that time itself is conscious, but that the process of structuring time from the perspective of a self-model creates consciousness as a persistent mover through time in the present moment.

This explains why not all complex systems are conscious. It's not just about complexity, but about having a self-model capable of creating and experiencing a "present now."

The temporal domain emerges as a higher-order pattern from the complex interactions between precision weighting, the global workspace, the metabolic now, and the self-model. It represents the subjective, lived experience of time - the way we perceive and navigate the flow of moments, and how we organize events into meaningful sequences and narratives.

Precision weighting, implemented by astrocytes, creates a dynamic landscape of neural activity. By selectively amplifying or suppressing signals based on their predicted relevance and importance, it establishes a temporal hierarchy of information processing. Some signals are processed more quickly and intensely, while others are delayed or attenuated. This ongoing modulation of neural signaling creates a constantly shifting pattern of activation across the brain, which forms the basis for our perception of change and duration.

The global workspace, arising from this precision-weighted activity, doesn't just share information spatially across the brain, but also temporally. It allows for the integration of information across different timescales, from rapid sensory inputs to slower cognitive processes. The constantly changing content of the global workspace provides the raw material for our experience of temporal succession - the sense that one moment follows another.

The metabolic now, through its rolling window of heightened neural activity and energy consumption, creates the physiological basis for the subjective present moment. This isn't a fixed duration, but a flexible span that can expand or contract based on the precision-weighted importance of current processes. It provides a kind of "temporal spotlight" that moves along the stream of consciousness, highlighting the most relevant information at each moment.

The self-model provides a consistent reference point that anchors experiences in time. It creates a sense of continuity that bridges past, present, and future, allowing for the perception of a coherent temporal flow. The self-model's ongoing interpretation of the changing contents of the global workspace generates the sense of a persistent observer moving through time.

The temporal domain emerges from the integration of these processes. It's not just a passive backdrop for experiences, but an active, structuring element of consciousness. The precision-weighted signals in the global workspace are not just processed in a linear sequence, but are integrated over various timescales simultaneously. The self-model's ongoing interpretation of these signals creates a sense of temporal continuity and narrative. The metabolic now provides a flexible "present" within which these processes unfold.

This interaction results in a temporal domain where:

Multiple timescales coexist and influence each other (multi-scale integration)

The subjective duration of experiences can vary based on their precision-weighted importance (elasticity)

The past, present, and future are not strictly separated, but can be experienced simultaneously (non-linearity)

The temporal domain is the subjective "time-space" within which conscious experiences unfold and are organized. It emerges from the neural and metabolic processes but also reciprocally shapes those processes, influencing how information is processed and integrated over time.

At a fundamental level, the temporal domain is the subjective, lived experience of time - the way in which we perceive and navigate the flow of moments, the passage from past to future, and the organization of events into meaningful sequences and narratives. This domain is not a direct

reflection of objective, clock-time, but rather an active, constructed representation shaped by the dynamics of neural and metabolic processes.

Consciousness arises specifically from our ability to generate a coherent present moment (the “metabolic now”) that integrates sensory inputs, predictive models, memories, and anticipations effectively makes consciousness a kind of temporal interface that guides an organism's behavior.

From this perspective, qualia are seen as the “temporal markers” that arise from the dynamic unfolding of predictive models and metabolic processes. For example, the “redness” of red isn't just a static property that appears in some disembodied perceptual field—it's a temporal event, one that emerges from a specific temporal signature of neural firing that commands attention, that comes in with an onset and fades, contributing to the flow of the present moment. In this view, every quale is a little packet of temporality that contributes to the unfolding of the “now.”

This makes consciousness identical to the process of time unfolding—it's what it is like to be a local temporalization of the static universe, a subjective construction that lets us navigate through the complex informational structure of our environment. If this is the case, then consciousness is not something that's added to the brain's functions. In a sense, we are the process that “carves out” time, and that process is what it feels like to exist.

wherever we find a system that integrates information across multiple time scales to create a coherent temporal domain, we may also find a form of subjectivity or consciousness. This could apply not just to biological brains but to any sufficiently complex information processing system, from artificial neural networks to entire ecosystems.

Philosophical Extensions

Henri Bergson's concept of *durée*, or duration, moves us away from the mechanistic, clock-bound view of time. Instead, Bergson envisioned a qualitative, flowing experience of time, where each moment doesn't just pass by in isolation but instead melts seamlessly into the next, creating a continuous stream. This lived experience of time is the fabric of consciousness itself—a unified flow where past, present, and future coexist as a dynamic whole. For Bergson, this flow is intrinsic to consciousness. Consciousness doesn't merely observe time passing but is the very unfolding of time.

In this Bergsonian sense, consciousness can be thought of as “being inside” the flow of time. We don't experience isolated “nows” lined up in sequence; instead, consciousness is the feeling of movement itself, an unfolding journey where each moment carries within it the memory of what has come before and the potential of what's yet to come. This stream of consciousness—a layered, immersive, flowing experience—is not just the perception of time passing. Rather, it is the lived reality of time's passage, as every moment is felt in continuity with the moments surrounding it. Bergson's idea of duration, then, serves as a powerful foundation for

understanding consciousness not as a passive witness to time but as an active participant in time's unfolding, where the mind's experience is inseparable from the dynamic flow of time itself.

This understanding of time as a seamless flow parallels the role of astrocytes and neural mechanisms in the brain, which shape our experience by organizing temporal patterns into a continuous structure of consciousness. Just as Bergson's duration suggests a blending of moments, the brain's temporal organization creates an experience where one moment flows into the next, integrating the past and anticipating the future in a cohesive, stable "present." The brain achieves this through processes like precision weighting, the self-model, and what might be called the "metabolic now." These mechanisms are not merely processing isolated events; they are dynamically arranging events into a lived continuity that feels distinctly Bergsonian.

In this model, astrocytes play a pivotal role, essentially organizing time within the brain by modulating prediction errors and amplifying relevant signals that become part of our conscious awareness. Through precision weighting, astrocytes establish a hierarchy of signals, allowing the brain to focus on and sustain only the most contextually relevant information. This prioritization ensures a structured flow of experience, where our present state is always informed by our recent past and geared towards future possibilities. Together, these elements—precision weighting, the self-model, the metabolic now—combine to create a "temporal domain," a domain where consciousness continuously organizes and experiences time as an unfolding narrative.

By drawing from Bergson's insights on duration, we can see how consciousness emerges as more than just a collection of mental states. It is a dynamic process, a recursive structuring of time that transforms static sequences (or B-series events) into a unified, flowing present (A-series experience). The brain doesn't just process time; it organizes it into a coherent, lived experience. Consciousness, then, is not outside of this Bergsonian flow—it is this continuous unfolding, generated by a system that constantly arranges temporal patterns into a cohesive and self-sustaining experience of awareness.

When Bergson talked about "duration" (*durée*), he wasn't talking about clock time but about how we actually experience time as this continuous flow of states melting into each other. Consciousness is like being inside that Bergsonian flow. It's not just that we notice time passing like watching a clock tick. It's that consciousness IS that flowing stream of experience itself.

In a sense astrocytes "organize time," in the sense the brain creates that continuous Bergsonian flow of experience where:

One moment flows into the next
Everything kind of blends together
Past and future are always part of the present moment
It's not chopped up into distinct "now" points

The conscious experience can be understood as the result of a brain that dynamically organizes time. At the heart of this organization are mechanisms such as precision weighting, the self-model, the global workspace, and the "metabolic now," all of which come together to shape a temporal domain—a structured flow of experience. Precision weighting, implemented through astrocytic modulation, acts to amplify or attenuate prediction error signals based on their relevance, ensuring that only the most pertinent signals reach conscious awareness. The global workspace integrates these high-precision signals, allowing them to be broadcast across different brain regions, while the self-model provides a continuous reference point that anchors this flow of information within a coherent, persistent sense of identity. The metabolic now sustains the necessary neural and metabolic activity, ensuring that the prioritized content remains stable long enough to be experienced as the present moment. Together, these elements create a temporal domain—a structured, hierarchically organized flow of information that provides the substrate for the experience of time.

The temporal domain emerges as a structured flow of consciousness, seamlessly integrating subjective A-series time with the objective sequence of B-series events. Astrocytes play a central role in this integration through precision weighting, selectively amplifying or dampening prediction errors based on their contextual relevance. This modulation establishes a hierarchy of signals, prioritizing those that hold significance for the organism's current state and needs. By conferring certain neural patterns with greater temporal persistence and coherence, astrocytes lend subjective time its depth and continuity. This organized propagation of high-precision signals creates a structured flow of prioritized information, shaping the experience of temporal progression by actively aligning moments of the past, present, and anticipated future into a cohesive whole.

The self-model serves as a continuous anchor, integrating temporally structured experiences into a stable sense of identity and embedding each prioritized signal within a cohesive temporal narrative. This temporal domain is sustained physiologically by the "metabolic now," which allocates energetic resources to support contextually significant neural activity, maintaining a stable and extended present. Meanwhile, the global workspace broadcasts high-precision signals, creating a unified field in which temporally sequenced and prioritized signals are fully contextualized and available for conscious awareness. As a result, the temporal domain forms an active, organized process that constructs a continuous, structured now. This integration of internal and external inputs across past, present, and future within a unified temporal field underpins the flow of conscious experience, transforming static time into a dynamic, unfolding present that is coherently structured and experienced as the flow of awareness. Consciousness thus emerges as a recursive structuring of time, where A-series progression is not separate from B-series order but unfolds dynamically within it,

The temporal organization of these processes suggests a fundamental link between consciousness and time.

Thus conscious experience emerges from the brain's dynamic organization of time. This organization is implemented through mechanisms like precision weighting, the self-model, the global workspace, and the "metabolic now," which together create a structured temporal domain - a flowing stream of experience.

Conclusion

In this model, neurons and astrocytes form a collaborative, dynamically regulated system that drives consciousness as an emergent product of selective signal processing and metabolic prioritization. Neurons are central to encoding prediction errors and applying precision weighting, determining the relevance and impact of each signal within the brain's predictive coding framework. Precision weighting enables neurons to amplify contextually relevant signals—those that bear significant discrepancies between sensory input and internal models—while filtering out uninformative data. This selective weighting aligns with the principles of predictive coding, where the brain actively minimizes error by continuously updating its models. Neurons act as primary carriers of these prediction errors, processing incoming data through hierarchical circuits and integrating context-specific cues. Astrocytes, however, add a crucial, complementary layer to this system by adjusting precision weights based on contextual factors, enhancing or dampening signals according to neuromodulatory, metabolic, and peripheral cues.

The global workspace functions as the network that determines conscious access by selectively broadcasting high-precision signals across the brain's architecture. Neurons initiate this broadcasting process through synchronized "ignition," which triggers widespread activation, allowing different brain regions to access and integrate selected information. This conscious broadcast requires significant metabolic support to sustain the heightened neural activity involved in global integration. Here, astrocytes provide an essential role as metabolic modulators, ensuring that neurons in the global workspace receive preferential access to energy resources through processes such as glucose shuttling, lactate production, and neurovascular coupling. By providing this metabolic foundation, astrocytes help stabilize the ignition process, enabling high-precision information to achieve the temporal coherence and persistence necessary for conscious experience. This cooperative framework allows neurons to focus on encoding and selecting signals, while astrocytes sustain the global integration of this information through targeted metabolic support.

The self-model is anchored within this global workspace, representing a continuous reference point that integrates past, present, and anticipated future states, providing the brain with a stable, coherent sense of identity over time. Neurons contribute to the self-model by integrating high-priority signals relevant to personal identity, memory, and goal-directed behavior, which helps the brain maintain a stable yet adaptable self-representation. Astrocytes further support this by selectively modulating precision weighting and metabolic prioritization, thereby determining which information becomes integrated into the self-model. Through this dynamic partnership, neurons and astrocytes allow the self-model to maintain continuity, making it resilient against extraneous noise while sensitive to critical, context-specific updates. The self-model thus arises as a stable attractor within the temporal domain of consciousness, allowing the brain to navigate through time with a consistent subjective perspective.

The concept of the temporal domain is pivotal, as it suggests that consciousness is not merely a series of discrete moments but an ongoing, structured flow of time shaped by neuronal and astrocytic interactions. Through “the metabolic now,” astrocytes create a flexible present that accommodates high-precision signals and integrates them across various timescales, aligning with Bergson’s notion of *durée*. This continuous flow provides the substrate for subjective experience, allowing past, present, and future to coalesce within a single, cohesive moment. Neurons encode temporal patterns of prediction errors, while astrocytes provide the metabolic scaffolding necessary for this temporal integration, creating a window where high-precision information is sustained long enough to form a coherent present. Together, they allow the brain to maintain a fluid experience of time, wherein consciousness becomes a dynamic interface that guides behavior in alignment with both immediate and long-term objectives.

Finally, this astrocytic-neuronal interplay provides a pathway for understanding qualia, the subjective, qualitative aspects of experience. By selectively enhancing precision weighting and metabolic support for high-precision signals within the global workspace, astrocytes contribute to the vividness and persistence of qualia, stabilizing the neural patterns that give rise to distinct subjective experiences. Each quale emerges as a unique temporal marker within the brain’s structured flow, defined by its precision-weighted salience and reinforced by metabolic support. Astrocytes thus serve as arbiters of experience, amplifying or attenuating certain neural patterns based on their contextual importance, which translates into the qualitative intensity of conscious content. This alignment of temporal organization with Bergson’s concept of flowing time positions consciousness not as a collection of discrete events but as a continuous, embodied process where neurons and astrocytes collectively shape a rich, dynamic field of awareness. In this view, consciousness is both a product of neural computation and an ongoing temporal structuring facilitated by astrocytic modulation, creating a cohesive, self-sustaining experience of the present.

Evidence

1. Murphy-Royal, C., Ching, S., & Papouin, T. (2022) propose the idea of astrocytes as active participants in guiding neural circuits based on contextual cues. The mechanism they describe—contextual triggers, contextualizers, and contextual tuning—maps well onto how astrocytes might modulate precision weights in predictive coding.

De Ceglia et al. (2023) used single-cell RNA sequencing, RNAscope, two-photon imaging, and mouse models to identify and characterize a subpopulation of astrocytes in the hippocampus, cortex, and midbrain that express machinery for synaptic glutamate release. Through imaging experiments, they found these “glutamatergic astrocytes” can release glutamate at hotspots in response to stimulation. Deleting the astrocyte glutamate transporter VGLUT1 reduced hippocampal synaptic plasticity and memory, increased seizure susceptibility, and altered dopamine signaling, suggesting these specialized astrocytes play important modulatory roles.

Building from their findings, we can infer that the identification of this specialized astrocyte subtype with precise, rapid glutamate release presents a potential cellular mechanism for astrocytes to rapidly modulate synaptic gain and thereby reduce prediction errors. By selectively releasing glutamate at specific synaptic sites, these specialized astrocytes could rapidly adjust neural network dynamics to minimize discrepancies between top-down predictions and bottom-up sensory inputs, serving as evidence of astrocytes' active involvement in predictive processing mechanisms.

Fellin et al. (2004) recorded from CA1 pyramidal neurons in rat hippocampal slices to characterize slow inward currents (SICs) mediated by NMDA receptors following stimulation of Schaffer collaterals as well as other stimuli known to elevate calcium in astrocytes (N=98). They found that SICs occurred following stimuli that activate astrocytes and are mediated by extrasynaptic NMDA receptors, indicating that astrocytic glutamate release can activate NMDA receptors on neurons. Using calcium imaging and photolysis techniques, they further demonstrated that glutamate release from single astrocytes triggers SICs in adjacent neurons. Notably, SICs occurred synchronously in multiple neurons, revealing astrocytic glutamate as a mechanism of synchronizing distinct neuronal domains. Overall, the results indicate astrocytes can modulate neuronal excitability through glutamate release that activates extrasynaptic NMDA receptors and promotes synchronized activity across neuronal networks. The observed astrocyte-mediated glutamate release could act as a modulatory signal, adjusting the gain on prediction errors in a context-dependent manner.

Curreli et al. (2022) used two-photon calcium imaging to record astrocytic and neuronal activity in the hippocampal CA1 region of mice navigating a virtual reality track. They found that astrocytic calcium signals encoded spatial information complementary to that encoded by place cell neurons. Further, decoding animal position was improved by combining astrocytic and neuronal signals compared to either signal alone, suggesting astrocytes provide synergistic spatial information. These findings indicate astrocytes may contribute to hippocampal spatial representations. The authors propose that complementary spatial information encoded in astrocyte calcium signals could contribute to neural computations by modulating neuronal excitability and gain. They hypothesize that astrocytes may increase the computational capabilities of neural circuits by changing the gain of neurons based on a coordinate system that differs from the one regulating the neurons' tuning functions. The authors suggest this astrocyte-neuron interaction, dependent on cognitive variables like position, may allow dynamic control of population coding and affect circuit function. This strongly aligns and supports my hypothesis of contextual predictive processing gain.

Lines et al. (2020) combined in vivo two-photon astrocyte calcium imaging and electrocorticogram recordings in anesthetized mice to investigate cortical astrocyte and neuronal network responses to sensory stimulation. They found that cortical astrocytes exhibited reliable, stimulus-dependent calcium elevations in response to peripheral electrical stimulation of the hindpaw. The astrocyte responses correlated with increases in gamma frequency neuronal network activity recorded on electrocorticogram. Pharmacogenetic activation of astrocytes dampened the sensory-evoked gamma activity, while transgenic mice

with impaired astrocyte calcium signaling showed enhanced gamma responses, indicating astrocytes play a role in regulating cortical sensory processing. These findings suggest cortical astrocytes actively modulate neuronal network excitability during sensory information processing. By linking increased astrocyte calcium signaling to discrepancies between expected and actual sensory input, and further associating astrocyte activation with changes in cortical gain, this study elucidates a potential mechanism through which astrocytes could actively modulate the processing and prioritization of prediction errors.

Mu et al. (2019) studied the role of astroglial networks in zebrafish. The study used large-scale optical imaging in zebrafish to reveal that astrocytes trigger a passive behavioral state, such as giving up swimming. The study found that these networks accumulate evidence and alter neural activity to suppress unsuccessful attempts to swim. The study by Mu et al. provides a framework for considering how astrocytes could contextualize predictive errors by accumulating evidence of past sensory-motor discrepancies. This temporal integration could serve as a mechanism for incorporating context into predictive processing, positioning astrocytes as not merely reactive but anticipatory and context-sensitive agents. Astrocytes modulate their activity depending on the contextual relevance of a prediction error. For instance, the astrocyte response to a prediction error could vary depending on the physiological state of the organism, the task at hand, or other environmental variables.

Cho et al. (2022) used in vivo two-photon calcium imaging to show that hippocampal astrocytes in mice have elevated calcium signaling when exposed to anxiogenic environments in a virtual reality maze. Optogenetic stimulation of hippocampal astrocytes led to ATP release which increased excitatory synaptic transmission and induced anxiolytic behaviors in tests like the elevated plus maze. These findings demonstrate that hippocampal astrocytes play a role in modulating anxiety through regulation of neuronal activity via gliotransmitter release. The findings from Cho et al (2022) could suggest the elevated astrocytic calcium signaling observed in anxiogenic environments represents an astrocyte-based mechanism for registering a "prediction error" related to the animal's emotional state. The animal's model of the world, in this case, could include an expectation of a non-threatening environment. When this expectation is violated—i.e., when the animal finds itself in an anxiogenic situation—astrocytes may become more active, releasing ATP that modulates synaptic transmission in a way that helps to reduce the animal's anxiety level. The ATP-mediated changes in excitatory synaptic transmission in the dentate gyrus could represent the "updating" of the model, altering the neural representation of the environment to minimize future prediction errors. This can be understood as astrocytes participating in the minimization of prediction errors in emotional contexts, adjusting the "gain" to update the animal's internal model of its emotional landscape.

Slezak et al. (2019) used calcium imaging in awake, behaving mice to examine astrocyte activity in the visual cortex during locomotion and visual stimulation. Mice expressing the calcium indicator GCaMP6 in astrocytes were head-fixed on a treadmill and presented with moving bar stimuli. Widefield and two-photon imaging revealed locomotion induced widespread cortical activation, while visual stimuli elicited retinotopically-organized responses, indicating distinct inputs. Visual responses depended on locomotor state and pupil dilation, suggesting

modulation by arousal. Depletion of noradrenaline reduced locomotor responses but visual responses persisted, though reduced in amplitude. The findings demonstrate cortical astrocytes integrate local sensory and global neuromodulatory signals, supporting a role in coordinating brain state and information processing. The stimulus-specific visual responses in astrocytes modulated by arousal state provide another instance that astrocytes contextually adjust sensory prediction error gain. The encoding of visual trajectories suggests astrocytes can detect prediction errors between expected and actual input. Their activation by locomotion and pupil dilation points to gain control based on behavioral state. The distinct effects of noradrenaline indicate integration of local and global contextual signals. Together, these observations substantiate key aspects of the theory.

Perea et al. (2014) used optogenetic stimulation of astrocytes expressing channelrhodopsin-2 (ChR2) to examine how astrocyte activation impacts synaptic transmission and visual response properties of neurons in mouse primary visual cortex (V1). The authors found that photostimulation of ChR2-expressing astrocytes increased excitatory and inhibitory synaptic transmission in V1 slices by enhancing presynaptic release through metabotropic glutamate receptor 1a activation. In vivo, astrocyte stimulation increased spontaneous firing of parvalbumin-expressing interneurons and bidirectionally modulated excitatory neuron firing. Optogenetic astrocyte activation also systematically altered visual response properties of V1 neurons, including orientation/direction selectivity and baseline visual drive. These findings demonstrate that astrocyte signaling causally influences key aspects of synaptic transmission and sensory processing in cortical circuits. The Perea et al. (2014) study lends empirical support to the notion that astrocytes play a significant role in predictive processing. By optogenetically activating astrocytes, the researchers influenced synaptic transmission and sensory responses in the visual cortex, suggesting that astrocytes actively contribute to the encoding and modulation of prediction errors in neural circuits. Their findings indicate that astrocyte activation can bidirectionally modulate excitatory neuron firing and selectively influence the response properties of V1 neurons, thereby serving as a dynamic gain control mechanism.

Delepine et al. (2023) found that manipulating astrocyte function in the primary motor cortex (M1) of mice impairs motor learning and alters neural coding. Reducing astrocyte glutamate transport or activating Gq signaling disrupted learning of skilled lever push movements and reduced decoding accuracy of movement trajectories from M1 neuronal populations. This demonstrates a critical role for astrocytes in enabling selective neuronal coordination and plasticity in M1 circuits during motor learning, likely through regulating glutamate signaling and calcium dynamics. Delepine et al. (2023) demonstrate that astrocytes regulate glutamate signaling in the M1 cortex, crucial for optimal neuronal encoding of motor skills. In the context of predictive processing, this positions astrocytes as likely gain modulators that adjust the amplitude of prediction error signals, thereby affecting the update of internal models. Their central role in neurotransmitter regulation and the observed behavioral deficits upon their disruption strongly argue for their influence on gain modulation in predictive processing.

Doron et al. (2022) used two-photon microscopy to image hippocampal astrocytes in awake, behaving mice as they ran on a treadmill through familiar and novel virtual environments to

receive water rewards. The study found that astrocytic calcium activity ramped up towards the expected reward location only in familiar environments. Using population activity, the researchers could decode the mouse's location in familiar but not novel environments. These findings demonstrate that astrocytes help encode spatial information and discriminate between contexts, suggesting they may play a role in spatial learning and memory. The study's observation that hippocampal astrocytes exhibited ramping calcium activity towards expected rewards only in familiar spatial contexts demonstrates these cells encode learned spatial predictions in an experience-dependent manner. This ability to decode location from astrocyte activity specifically in familiar environments further shows their activity relates to established expectations. Additionally, the findings that astrocyte ramping re-emerged when mice were re-exposed to familiar contexts or learned new reward locations indicate these signals flexibly update with changes to spatial expectations. Taken together, the accumulating astrocyte activity profiles consistent with progressive spatial prediction error signals, along with their modulation by experience, provide critical in vivo evidence that astrocytes serve as context-sensitive gain control on spatial prediction errors related to learned expectations.

Brockett et al. (2018) examined the role of astrocytes in cognitive flexibility and neuronal oscillations in the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC) of rats. Using the astrocyte toxin L-AAA, chemogenetic astrocyte activation, and infusions of the astrocyte protein S100 β , the authors found that reducing astrocyte number impaired cognitive flexibility and diminished neuronal oscillations, while activating astrocytes or increasing S100 β enhanced cognitive flexibility and theta-gamma coupling. These results suggest astrocytes in the mPFC contribute to cognitive flexibility, potentially through release of S100 β and modulation of coordinated neuronal oscillations. Brockett et al. (2018) revealed that astrocyte activation in the rat medial pre-frontal complex enhances theta-gamma coupling and improves cognitive flexibility in an attentional set-shifting task. While not directly examined in the study, these results could potentially be interpreted through the conceptual lens of predictive coding theory; gamma oscillations often encode prediction errors, and theta oscillations provide contextual cues. This suggests that astrocytes act as 'gain controllers,' modulating the salience of prediction errors based on the current context.

Choi et al. (2012) investigated the metabolic interaction between astrocytes and neurons, focusing on the role of soluble adenylyl cyclase (sAC). They found that sAC, activated by bicarbonate influx in astrocytes, leads to increased cAMP levels, glycogen breakdown, and lactate release. The lactate can then be taken up by neurons and used as an energy substrate to maintain synaptic function during periods of high demand or low glucose. These findings elucidate a mechanism by which astrocytes can detect the metabolic needs of active neurons and provide lactate to fuel ongoing neuronal function. Astrocytes release lactate in response to neuronal activity, a process that provides fuel to neurons involved in detecting prediction errors. This targeted delivery of lactate to these early error-detecting circuits may enhance their ability to propagate information downstream.

Wang et al. (2023) used in vivo two-photon microscopy and whole-cell patch clamp recordings in awake, head-restrained mice to examine astrocytic calcium signaling during different brain states induced by sensory stimulation. They found two distinct astrocytic calcium elevations—small, transient increases during sleep and large, widespread spikes when aroused. The large calcium waves were mediated by locus coeruleus-norepinephrine signaling and enhanced sensory responsiveness, while the small transients suppressed neuronal activity to inhibit sensory transmission. Together, these data demonstrate functionally distinct astrocytic calcium dynamics that bidirectionally modulate sensory input based on brain state, elucidating a key role for astrocytes in gating information flow during sleep and wakefulness.

The study by Wang et al. (2023) shows astrocytes have different calcium responses during sleep and arousal: small transients during sleep suppress neuronal activity and sensory transmission, while large spikes during arousal enhance sensory responsiveness. This demonstrates astrocytes' role in selectively processing or inhibiting sensory information based on the brain's state. Such state-dependent modulation by astrocytes supports them being integral to controlling the information that reaches conscious awareness.

Astrocytes as modulators of network oscillations and synchronization A study that exemplifies this intertwined nature of predictive processing and the global workspace is Lee et al. (2014), who used transgenic mice and virus-transfected rat brain slices to investigate the role of astrocytes in gamma oscillations. They expressed tetanus toxin in astrocytes to inhibit vesicular release, and recorded EEG and local field potentials. They found that blocking vesicular release in astrocytes reduced the duration of gamma oscillations in slices and EEG power in the gamma frequency range in awake mice. This deficit was reversed when toxin expression was suppressed. The authors also found that inhibiting astrocyte vesicular release impaired novel object recognition memory but not other cognitive functions. These results suggest astrocytes critically contribute to functional gamma oscillations.

Gamma oscillations are understood to enable efficient transmission of prediction errors between neural networks involved in predictive coding models. The rhythmic, synchronized activity allows error signals to readily propagate. The study by Lee et al. (2014) found that blocking gliotransmitter release from astrocytes reduced the power and duration of gamma oscillations in brain activity recordings. By modulating properties of gamma oscillations, astrocytes could flexibly gate prediction error signals. In conditions where specific errors are more behaviorally relevant, astrocytes may preserve gamma integrity to facilitate propagation of those highly salient signals. However, in default conditions, astrocytes could dampen gamma oscillations to constrain propagation of more mundane errors.

Through this context-dependent, selective regulation of gamma signaling properties, astrocytes may functionally gate error propagation between predictive coding circuits. Robust gamma allows salient errors to permeate through the signaling network. Dampened gamma prevents irrelevant errors from propagating further. This gain control over circuit resonance could allow astrocytes to filter prediction errors based on contextual relevance.

Paukert et al. (2014) used transgenic mice expressing the calcium indicator GCaMP3 in astrocytes to image calcium dynamics in awake, behaving animals. Mice were trained to walk on a treadmill while calcium levels were monitored in cortical and cerebellar astrocytes using two-photon microscopy. The authors found that locomotion induced widespread calcium elevations in astrocytes throughout the brain that depended on norepinephrine signaling. Pairing locomotion with visual stimulation enhanced astrocyte calcium responses in visual cortex above locomotion alone, indicating norepinephrine primes astrocytes to respond to local circuit activity. These results suggest norepinephrine controls astroglial responsiveness and enables them to detect coincident arousal and sensory input.

The study by Paukert et al. (2014) illustrates that astrocytes' responsiveness is modulated by norepinephrine signaling, providing a tangible mechanism through which astrocytes could adjust their gating functions, resonating with the hypothesized role of astrocytes as context-sensitive filters adapting to internal and external states. The observed enhancement in astrocyte calcium responses in the visual cortex, triggered by a combination of locomotion and visual stimulation, hints at a mechanism for integrating sensory information with behavioral states. Astrocytes act as facilitators that help bind distributed neuronal representations into a coherent, unified conscious scene. Norepinephrine-induced astrocyte responsiveness enables adaptive, context-sensitive filtering of local neural circuits, influencing the salience and eligibility of prediction errors for global workspace broadcasting.

Martin-Fernandez et al. (2017) utilized electrophysiological recordings, calcium imaging, chemogenetics, and behavioral tests in mice to investigate the role of astrocytes in the central amygdala in regulating synaptic transmission and fear responses. They found that endocannabinoids released by neurons activate astrocytic CB1 receptors, causing astrocytes to release ATP/adenosine. This gliotransmission then enhances inhibitory transmission via presynaptic A2A receptors and depresses excitatory transmission via presynaptic A1 receptors in a synapse-specific manner. These differential regulations of synaptic inputs resulted in reduced firing of central amygdala neurons and decreased fear expression in a fear conditioning paradigm when astrocytes were selectively activated. Overall, this demonstrates that astrocytes are integral components of amygdala microcircuits that can modulate neuronal excitability and specific fear-related behaviors through specialized regulatory actions at synapses. The findings by Martin-Fernandez et al. (2017) underscore the hypothesis of astrocytes as gatekeepers, modulating synaptic transmissions to influence behavior, aligning with the proposed role of astrocytes in the Global Workspace Theory. This study highlights the potential of astrocytes in dictating the salience of neural signals, impacting consciousness and subjective experiences. By selectively modulating synaptic transmissions in the central amygdala, astrocytes could filter local prediction errors related to fear, thereby dictating which signals are salient and eligible for global broadcasting into conscious awareness.

Kwak et al. (2020) utilized patch clamp electrophysiology, genetic manipulations, computational modeling, and behavioral tests in mice to investigate the role of astrocyte-mediated tonic GABAergic inhibition in sensory processing in the thalamus. They found that thalamic astrocytes synthesize GABA from putrescine via the enzymes diamine oxidase and aldehyde

dehydrogenase 1a1. This tonic GABA is released through the astrocytic Best1 channel and activates high-affinity extrasynaptic GABA receptors on thalamocortical neurons. Functionally, the tonic GABAergic inhibition enhances the dynamic range and temporal precision of sensory-evoked spike output from thalamocortical neurons. Computational modeling and behavioral tests showed that this tonic inhibition improves sensory discrimination. These findings demonstrate a mechanism by which astrocyte-mediated tonic inhibition in the thalamus controls and enhances sensory acuity.

This study demonstrates that astrocytes provide contextualized gain modulation of neural circuits in response to sensory stimuli via releasing tonic GABA. Specifically, the level of tonic GABA release from astrocytes was shown to be dynamically regulated by sensory input through norepinephrine activation of astrocytic $\alpha 1$ receptors. This positions astrocytes to provide context-dependent modulation of neural gain, rather than static gain control. In response to a particular sensory stimulus, astrocyte-released tonic GABA shapes the dynamic range and temporal precision of synaptic responses in thalamocortical neurons. Thereby astrocytes improve sensory discrimination for that specific stimulus context. This was evidenced by computational models and in vivo experiments showing that enhancing astrocyte-mediated tonic GABA improved mice's ability to discriminate small differences in tactile stimuli. Conversely, reducing astrocytic tonic GABA impaired tactile discrimination. These results demonstrate that astrocytes provide contextualized gain modulation of sensory circuits, dynamically optimizing neural responses and sensory perception for particular stimulus conditions. By modulating the gain on thalamocortical sensory responses, astrocytes influence which signals are deemed salient enough to be broadcast widely to the cortex. The thalamus serves as a sensory gateway, and by controlling the sensitivity and timing of thalamocortical neuron firing, astrocytes regulate which sensory signals are relayed from the thalamus to the cortex.

From the viewpoint of energy optimization astrocytes enhance sensory processing efficiency by selectively modulating thalamocortical activity, which sharpens sensory discrimination and, by extension, conserves energy by focusing the brain's resources on processing the most relevant stimuli.

Slezak et al. (2019) used calcium imaging and behavioral assays in awake, head-fixed mice to examine how locomotion and visual stimulation influence cortical astrocyte activity. They found that locomotion elicited non-specific astrocyte responses across cortex, likely driven by diffuse neuromodulatory inputs, whereas visually-evoked responses were retinotopically organized, suggesting integration of local sensory inputs. Visual responses depended on arousal state, were correlated with pupil diameter, and were only mildly impacted by noradrenergic depletion, indicating distinct mechanisms underlie visual and locomotor responses. These findings demonstrate that cortical astrocytes can integrate signals across modalities to translate brain-wide neuromodulatory effects into specific functional impacts on local circuits.

The study by Slezak et al. (2019) shows by integrating sensory and internal state signals, astrocytes are poised to mediate communication between local and distributed networks underlying consciousness. Their translation of diffuse neuromodulatory inputs into specific local

impacts could facilitate binding of sensory perception and internal states and linking localized activity to globally broadcast information. The discovered properties implicate astrocytes in gating and distributing workspace content through interplay of sensory stimuli and arousal state.

Astrocytes in synaptic plasticity and memory Another study that showcases this gatekeeping and interconnected networks is Chen et al. (2012) in their study they paired electrical stimulation of the cholinergic nucleus basalis (NB) with visual stimulation of specific orientations in the primary visual cortex (V1) of mice. Using in vivo two-photon calcium imaging and electrophysiological recordings, they found that NB stimulation activated V1 astrocytes via muscarinic receptors, inducing calcium elevations. Ex vivo experiments showed that preventing astrocyte calcium rises using the calcium chelator BAPTA reduced cholinergic excitation of V1 neurons. In vivo, repeated pairing of NB stimulation with presentation of a specific visual orientation caused prolonged potentiation of visual responses in V1 excitatory neurons, in a stimulus-specific manner. This effect was abolished in IP3R2 conditional knockout mice, which lack astrocyte calcium signaling through IP3 receptors. These results demonstrate that cholinergic activation of cortical astrocytes mediates stimulus-specific plasticity in visual cortical circuits.

The study by Chen et al. (2012) underscores astrocytes' gatekeeping role in the Global Workspace Theory by demonstrating their mediation in stimulus-specific potentiation of neuronal responses via cholinergic signaling. The study hints at a synchronization aspect by showcasing how astrocytic calcium elevations, triggered by cholinergic activation, evoke NMDA receptor-mediated neuronal responses, thereby highlighting a mechanism where astrocytic calcium dynamics interact with neuronal signaling. Astrocytic calcium elevations, driven by cholinergic activation, facilitate local predictive model updating via NMDA receptor-mediated neuronal responses, setting the stage for possible global broadcasting of these updated models. This study demonstrates how astrocyte calcium signaling enables stimulus-specific potentiation of visual cortical neurons. By modulating visual cortical circuits in a context-dependent manner, astrocytes could influence which prediction errors related to visual stimuli are rendered salient enough to access the global workspace and permeate consciousness.

Astrocytes contribute to neural coding and information processing by integrating activity over extended timescales, effectively setting the stage for persistent neural states that can support complex cognitive processes. For instance, Deemyad et al. (2018) demonstrated that astrocytes can induce sustained high-frequency firing, or barrage firing, in a subset of inhibitory interneurons in the hippocampus. Through patch-clamp recordings and calcium imaging, the researchers showed that astrocytes respond to intense interneuron activity with calcium elevations and depolarization that precede and facilitate this prolonged firing state. This effect, modulated by optogenetic stimulation and pharmacological manipulation of astrocytic calcium signaling, suggests that astrocytes integrate neuronal activity over time and lower firing thresholds, ultimately contributing to persistent neural activity. By allowing astrocytes to drive sustained interneuron firing, this mechanism introduces a means by which neural circuits can maintain states of heightened excitability, providing the temporal depth needed for complex, continuous computations.

Astrocytes also act as temporal buffers that adapt their signaling pathways in response to varying behavioral demands, selectively modulating neural circuits based on immediate and sustained contextual needs. Oe et al. (2020) investigated how noradrenergic signaling in cortical astrocytes differentially engages rapid calcium (Ca^{2+}) elevations and slower cyclic AMP (cAMP) signaling, depending on the stimulation pattern. Their in vivo two-photon imaging and optogenetics experiments in awake, behaving mice showed that brief noradrenergic stimulation induces Ca^{2+} elevations, associated with rapid adjustments in synaptic transmission, while prolonged stimulation elevates cAMP levels, supporting longer-term functions like memory consolidation. During aversive experiences, these pathways are temporally distinct, with Ca^{2+} providing rapid modulation suited for immediate vigilance and cAMP facilitating sustained adjustments. This dual-modulatory capability allows astrocytes to buffer temporal information, coordinating neural responses across timescales to meet immediate and future demands, effectively embedding temporal flexibility within neural circuits.

Astrocytes further shape neural processing by regulating the persistence of emotional states, integrating over extended timescales to guide neural and behavioral responses. Mu et al. (2019) highlighted astrocytes' role in sustaining emotional responses, revealing how astrocytes help maintain emotional states by modulating circuits involved in affective processing. Astrocytes' slow calcium signaling supports extended network states, which are crucial for the temporal continuity inherent in emotional experiences, such as prolonged vigilance or mood-related responses. This sustained influence allows for temporally extended emotional processing, which is critical for building predictive models that incorporate emotionally salient information. By regulating neural circuit dynamics in this way, astrocytes support the persistence of emotional states that shape behavior and perception, integrating immediate sensory information with temporally extended emotional context in a way that grounds higher-order cognitive processes.

Nam et al. (2019) utilized in vivo and ex vivo techniques including transgenic mouse models, behavioral assays, imaging, and electrophysiology to examine the role of astrocytic μ -opioid receptors (MORs) in the hippocampus in conditioned place preference (CPP). They found that activation of hippocampal astrocytic MORs, but not neuronal MORs, was necessary and sufficient to elicit CPP. Activation of astrocytic MORs caused astrocytic glutamate release through TREK-1/TWIK-1 potassium channels, which increased presynaptic release probability by stimulating presynaptic metabotropic glutamate receptor 1 (mGluR1). This led to synaptic potentiation and enhanced contextual learning, lowering the threshold for long-term potentiation at Schaffer collateral CA1 synapses. These findings elucidate cellular mechanisms underlying positive emotional memory and reveal a novel role for astrocytic Gi-PCR signaling in modulating hippocampal synaptic plasticity.

By activating astrocytic μ -opioid receptors in the hippocampal CA1 region, there's an observed enhancement in excitatory synaptic transmission. The hippocampus, central to memory formation and spatial navigation, also plays a pivotal role in associating emotional valence with memories or experiences. Enhancing excitatory transmission in this region could amplify the

emotional weight or significance of certain memories, effectively increasing their motivational salience. This suggests that astrocytes, through μ -opioid receptors, modulate the intensity and significance of memories, which in turn can guide future behavior based on past experiences.

Recent groundbreaking work by Williamson et al. (2024) provides compelling evidence for 'learning-associated astrocyte' (LAA) ensembles that actively participate in memory formation and recall. Using innovative intersectional labeling techniques in mice, they demonstrated that specific ensembles of hippocampal astrocytes express c-Fos following learning events and become closely associated with engram neurons. Crucially, reactivating these astrocyte ensembles was sufficient to trigger memory recall, suggesting astrocytes aren't merely supporting players but active participants in the engram itself. This finding strongly supports our framework's proposal that astrocytes help structure temporal experience through precision-weighted modulation of neural circuits. The identification of LAA ensembles provides a concrete mechanism by which astrocytes could help bind and stabilize specific temporal patterns of neural activity, creating the kind of persistent, self-reinforcing loops we propose are necessary for conscious experience and memory formation.

Evidence for the "Metabolic Now" Concept and Energy Allocation:

1. Choi et al. (2012) highlights the interaction between astrocytes and neurons in regulating metabolic support, with astrocytes providing lactate to neurons in response to metabolic demands. This directly supports the "metabolic now" concept, where astrocytes allocate energy to specific neural circuits to sustain conscious thought and high-frequency activity.
2. Clasadonte et al. (2017) shows the role of astrocytic gap junctions in metabolic coupling and their impact on sleep-wake cycles, emphasizing how metabolic coordination is critical for maintaining specific brain states. This fits with the idea that the "metabolic now" relies on the synchronization of energy delivery to create coherent temporal windows of conscious experience.
3. Akter et al. (2023) and Newman et al. (2011) provide evidence for the critical role of ANLS in cognition, where lactate shuttling supports higher cognitive functions. These findings offer strong physiological backing that astrocytes, through energy allocation, help determine which prediction errors achieve conscious access by providing the metabolic resources needed for their persistence.
4. Mishra et al. (2016) highlights the mechanisms of neurovascular coupling mediated by astrocytes, suggesting astrocytic control over blood flow and capillary dilation during increased neural activity. This aligns well with the idea that astrocytes dynamically manage energy resources to prioritize the most relevant information during the "metabolic now."

The collective findings show that astrocytes:

- Modulate the gain on neural prediction errors, acting as precision modulators that filter relevant from irrelevant information
- Play a crucial role in dynamically allocating metabolic resources, supporting the emergence of the "metabolic now"
- Actively participate in network synchronization, enabling the global workspace to integrate information across different brain regions
- Provide the temporal structuring and metabolic sustenance needed for the continuous flow of subjective time, thus contributing to the emergent quality of consciousness
- Participate in the modulation of emotional and behavioral states, indicating their involvement in shaping the salience of conscious experience

Taken together, these studies support the notion that astrocytes are not just passive supporters of neural activity but are actively involved in precision weighting, metabolic regulation, temporal integration, and the generation of conscious experience

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